

UBD SBE يو. بي. دي. ايس. بي. اي.
UBD SCHOOL OF BUSINESS AND ECONOMICS

UNIVERSITI BRUNEI DARUSSALAM

BB-2208 HUMAN RESOURCE MANAGEMENT

INDIVIDUAL ASSIGNMENT 2 - CASE STUDY ANALYSIS ON MARSYA FARM USING
THE GUEST MODEL OF HRM

REGISTRATION NUMBER: 19B8523

DATE OF SUBMISSION: 11th NOVEMBER, 2020 (WEDNESDAY)

CONTENTS

1. ABSTRACT	3
2. INTRODUCTION	4-5
2.1. Agriculture in Brunei.	4
2.2. Marsya Farm.	4-5
3. PROBLEM STATEMENT	5
4. CASE ANALYSIS USING THE GUEST MODEL OF HRM	5-7
4.1. Lack of Financial Support.	6
4.2. Lack of Support and Encouragement.	6
4.3. Lack of Knowledge and Expertise.	7
5. SOLUTIONS	7-9
5.1. Access to Finance.	7-8
5.2. Exposure to Agriculture.	8-9
5.3. Agricultural Proficiency.	9
6. CONCLUSION	9-10
7. RECOMMENDATIONS	10
8. REFERENCES	11

1. ABSTRACT

Marsya Farm is an established agribusiness that utilises more conventional methods by optimising new technologies with the objective of increasing its production by 2019 and 2020. It is owned and managed by an agripreneur named Awang Haji Muliadi bin Moxsin, and he also appears to be an agromentor. During his journey in the agricultural industry, he faces some challenges of having complexity and being less popular due to several factors: lack of access to finance, lack of community support and encouragement, and lack of knowledge and expertise in the agricultural field. These acknowledged issues may negatively impact Marsya Farm and therefore, they must be addressed. This case analysis aims to identify the root causes of the issues outlined by Haji Muliadi, as well as to suggest possible solutions in the context of HRM using The Guest Model with the aim to overcome those problems by suggesting the optimal solution, that is exposing his agribusiness through social media to attract more local and youth applicants and retain them.

2. INTRODUCTION

2.1. Agriculture in Brunei

Agriculture, including agrifood, is believed to be the fundamental source of the primary resources and manufacturing industries that assist to increase a country's economic growth by contributing to the growth domestic product (GDP) of the country, export, and economic diversification. For many years, Brunei has been greatly dependent on the contribution of oil and gas as the biggest driver of the economy's growth. The wealth and prosperity of Brunei, in fact, are derived from primarily its oil export as there was 85.2% of total exports of oil and gas in 2019 (Department of Economic Planning and Development [DEPS], 2020). However, oil and gas are non-renewable energy sources and are unsustainable, and in consequence, will inevitably run out over time in the future. This means that Brunei has to overcome its over-dependency on the exports of oil and gas and diversify its economy by progressing in other sectors like agriculture and agrifood industries.

Agriculture in Brunei appears to have a slow progression, in fact, there was a decline in the number of entrepreneurs venturing into the agriculture industries. Statistics have shown that between 2015 and 2018, there was a reduction of 4.1% in the number of agripreneurs (Department of Agriculture and Agrifood [DAA], 2018) and this may be caused by numerous challenges that hinder them to sustain in the industry. Nevertheless, the agricultural labour force has surprisingly increased by 2,318 employees, that was from 5,975 in 2015 to 8,293 in 2018.

2.2. Marsya Farm

Marsya Farm is one of the agricultural companies, owned by an agripreneur known as Awang Haji Muliadi bin Moksini. He began venturing into his farming enterprise in 2000 with only having land 1-hectare wide. It is located in *Kawasan Kemajuan Pertanian (KKP)*, Kampung Sungai Liang, Daerah Belait. Marsya Farm is a farming business exercising more conventional methods by utilising new technologies such as fertigation, drip irrigation, rain shelter and hydroponics. The company produces a variety of fruits and vegetables, particularly menas and mulberry, mustard leaf, cucumber, cherry tomatoes and corns. Further, Haji Muliadi's mission and vision of his business are to provide the highest quality product and pesticide-free crops in accordance with its

new patented logo that is "ALL ABOUT GREEN". Marsya Farm's targets for 2019 and 2020 are to increase its harvest to 85 tonnes and 95 tonnes respectively.

3. PROBLEM STATEMENT

Haji Muliadi as an agripreneur himself has faced some difficulties, especially at the introduction phase of his business. He was concerned with the shortage of monetary support from banks, inadequate moral support and encouragement from the locals and the lack of knowledge and proficiency in the agricultural field. These issues may restrain him to manage the human resources to perform effectively, resulting in difficulty to achieve the organisational goals. This study attempts to analyse the root causes of the problems, as well as developing and evaluating the solutions to overcome the issues in consideration of the Guest Model.

4. CASE ANALYSIS USING THE GUEST MODEL OF HRM

Figure 1 The Guest Model of HRM

The Guest Model is a management model of HRM that is developed by David Guest in 1997, covering six dimensions of analysis which this model proposes specific human resource management (HRM) strategies, demanding certain HRM practices in order to develop and result in different outcomes such as HR outcomes, behavioral, performance and financial outcomes (Figure 1). To put it another way, the financial outcomes are said to be relying on employee efficiency, which in turn is the effect of action-oriented employee behavior. As for the behavioral outcomes, it is the result of employee commitment, quality and flexibility which these results are

influenced by HR practices. The practices have to be in line with the HRM strategies which are integrated with the organisational strategies.

4.1. Lack of Financial Support

Aside from self-fund or family fund, financial aid in the form of loans or grants provided by the government or any loan institutions would be beneficial for a start-up. Haji Muliadi claimed that he had inadequate monetary support from banks as they would not approve his loan request. This was due to lending institutions often proposed firm rules to agripreneurs such as collateral was needed in order to proceed with the loan (Herbel, Croweley, & Lee, 2010). The only option to get financial support was to persuade his family members and his close friends to lend him money. This situation is common in Brunei as there is no stock exchange in the market. It is however reported that financial aid is the most critical and essential determinant of entrepreneurship (Dacin, Dacin, & Mataer, 2010), including agripreneurship. Though Haji Muliadi has successfully set up his agribusiness, the fact that having insufficient financial assistance from the bank may not be favorable in the long run for Haji Muliadi when there is a need to expand his business, involving the need to hire and train additional employees, as well as to buy new machinery.

4.2. Lack of Support and Encouragement

Furthermore, Haji Muliadi stated that poor support and encouragement were coming from almost everyone. There is less interest from the locals in farming and it is somewhat challenging to entice their interest. This is because the mentality in Brunei concerning agricultural jobs is that the standard of the job is very low and that people expect to just recruit foreign labour to perform farming manually as it is cheaper that way (Musa, Pg Hj Idris, & Basir, 2020). This creates the idea of farming as unappealing to the potential employee candidates as a consequence of it being traditional due to the outdated methods of farming, which therefore makes it difficult for agripreneurs to select and recruit the right human resource to perform the tasks. In relation to the difficulty of finding a well-competent employee for farming, this may be as a result of agriculture lacking exposure to the market as according to Musa, Idris, and Basir (2020), many people are unaware of the existence of agribusinesses, thus, resulting people to assume agribusiness is unprofitable.

4.3. Lack of Knowledge and Expertise

Moreover, Haji Muliadi experienced an obstacle during his start-up because he had insufficient knowledge and expertise in the agriculture field. As one of the people who finds it difficult to seek assistance, he had to self-taught himself by going thru a trial and error method until he was able to discover the right soil suitability. It is often difficult for agripreneurs to find qualified candidates that are able to carry out a precision farming. Without applying the right procedure of farming, this could deteriorate the quality of the output, resulting in a reduction of the effective production.

5. SOLUTIONS

5.1. Access to Finance

It is important that agripreneurs have access to finance as this can help them to grow and expand their agribusiness according to their organisational goals. As for Marsya Farm, its target is to increase its production and distribution of output to 85 tonnes in 2019 and 95 tonnes in 2020 which this not only involves solely finance, but also in terms of land and increasing its labour capacity. There has been a number of initiatives and provision of programmes introduced by the DAA with youth as being the main target of the ministry (Azlan Othman, 2019). As an example, one of the programmes being introduced was the Young Farmers Placement Project where 30 participants were provided a 10-acre piece of land, without having to pay the rental fee, provided with a home for free, also including a monthly allowance of approximately BND400. It was reported that most of them were committed to proceed with their small-scale vegetable production by utilising conventional farming methods (Azlan Othman, 2019).

More schemes like Young Farmers Placement Project should be implemented as farmers will not be able to get easy access to financing in order to meet the requirement to suffice the farming production costs, including the HR costs. This, at least, helps them to create a suitable condition for starting or continuing a business. Regardless of the scheme provision, youth should also not be over-reliant on it. Other than that, this will support Marsya Farm to get the latest advancement for farming as again according to Haji Muliadi, Marsya Farm practises conventional methods, which means they need to integrate biological and mechanical practices. Having a high-tech system of

farming, in this way, employees of Marsya Farm can take more responsibility and involvement by completing the tasks using the advanced machinery, increasing the flexibility of the workforce. In addition, this encourages employees to actively participate in the completion of the farming process whereby it will motivate employees because it serves as a symbol of the manager valuing his employee's feedback and work done. This will in turn improve productivity and overall efficiency.

5.2. Exposure to Agriculture

Providing early exposure to the youths in agriculture helps them to inculcate their interest in the agricultural industry making the applicant pool is greater for HR selection, thus, increases the chance of finding a competent employee who possibly has the passion and proficiency in the agricultural sector. Other than that, exposing them to the agriculture sector also helps to eradicate and dispel the myths and doubts of working within an agribusiness. The exposure can be done by mentoring them, including increasing awareness of the current situation of the agricultural industry. Agripreneurs themselves affirmed that exposing the youths to such practical and experiential-based knowledge plays a fundamental role in changing their perspectives and mindset towards agriculture (Musa, Idris, & Basir, 2020). For instance, in the case of Marsya Farm, training by mentoring them may somehow produce an increase in their future commitment to an agribusiness, building a well-cooperation within the business and resulting in higher productivity with a better quality of production, which this can act as a competitive advantage to Marsya Farm. This is because an appropriate HRM practice is associated with higher levels of satisfaction amongst employees (Guest, 2002).

According to The Global Digital Reports, it exceeds 3.8 billion people use social media globally with Brunei having the highest number of users consisting of 410,000 users (Azlan Othman, 2020). This shows a good indication of using social media as a platform to promote the agribusiness, especially Instagram, to give people an insight into an agriculture field and to find a better-suited potential employee to perform the agricultural activities. This is because Brunei has an Instagram penetration rate of 60 per cent of the population, that is reaching audiences totaling 210,000 users (Azlan Othman, 2020). This again will help to increase the support and encouragement from

people to be involved in the industry. However, the exposure of agriculture being carried out through social media may not be reliable as it may not reach to some people. This is because an approximate of 40 per cent of the world's population continues to be unconnected to the Internet (Azlan Othman, 2020). Therefore, it may disrupt the exposure of agribusiness through social media.

5.3. Agricultural Proficiency

As a successful agreementor who managed to overcome the challenge, Haji Muliadi seeks to provide training for his employees, or even the potential ones, especially the youths. This will help them to acquire the required skills for farming, leaving them to be equipped with accurate knowledge and skills of handling the farming process for example the irrigation system, and in exchange will motivate the employees as they know what they are doing. Though HR costs will be incurred by Marsya Farm due to sending their employees for training, this may also increase their commitment and the labour productivity and eventually enhance the cooperation between Marsya Farm management and the employees. For instance, according to Herzberg's theory, with more involvement of the employees as being able to do various different farming tasks will result in greater job enrichment, thus increasing their motivation due to the flexibility (Stimpson & Farquharson, 2010). Consequently, this may result in a lower labour turnover and lower absenteeism amongst the employees, resulting in an HR cost reduction in the long run as it will be a return on employee investment. As reported by Guest (2002), it is found that positive employee–management relations were associated with labour productivity. Not only that, there is also a positive link between commitment and higher corporate performance and it appears that the human resource (HR) practices, in this case, training by mentoring provided by Haji Muliadi, affect both employees' behavior and performance outcomes (Guest, 2002).

6. CONCLUSION

Agriculture has always been one of the mechanisms for Brunei to diversify its economy rather than to just be over-dependent on the export of oil and gas, and it also in fact has become the main source of income for the economy by contributing to the growth of Brunei's gross domestic product (GDP). However, there are still some challenges that are faced by Marsya Farm that may

negatively affect the agribusiness, including the HR management specifically putting the emphasis on selecting and recruiting employees because there has been a lack of interest in pursuing the agricultural industry and lack of support and encouragement from others due to the perception and myths that appear along with it. Other than that, lacking knowledge and expertise regarding the farming process is also one of the problems that has been outlined by Haji Muliadi. The way forward for Marsya Farm is to provide a mentoring programme to train their employees, or any potential youths, to involve them in the farming sector and also to stimulate their interest by making them understand how farming actually works by utilising conventional methods such as drip irrigation, fertigation, hydroponics and rain shelter, which these methods optimise the HR with the latest advancements and technologies to enhance their productivity and increase the output to achieve Marsya Farm's goal of 2019 and 2020, which are producing 85 tonnes and 95 tonnes respectively. In addition, by exposing the business to social media, particularly Instagram, it may help Marsya Farm to raise awareness of agricultural activities generally and will help to gain more support and encouragement.

7. RECOMMENDATIONS

The optimal solution to improve HR management of Marsya Farm is to use the social media platform, particularly Instagram, as it acts as a means of increasing awareness of the locals towards agribusiness in general. Not only that, it also coordinates with the Minister of Primary Resources and Tourism's aim of involving youth as being the main target to increase the number of agricultural output (Azlan Othman, 2019). This is because it is reported that Brunei has the second highest social media penetration rate of 117 per cent users, with mostly used by eligible audiences who are 13 years old and above (Azlan Othman, 2020). Therefore, it is sensible and favorable to use the method of exposing Haji Muliadi's business to attract more applicants of local youth and retain them as his employees.

8. REFERENCES

- Azlan Othman. (2020, February 10). Bruneians rank high in social media usage. *Borneo Bulletin*. Retrieved from <https://borneobulletin.com.bn/2020/02/bruneians-rank-high-social-media-usage/>
- Azlan Othman. (2019, March 25). Nod for motion to revive Young Farmers Programme. *Borneo Bulletin*. Retrieve from <https://borneobulletin.com.bn/2019/03/nod-for-motion-to-revive-young-farmers-programme/>
- Dacin, P., Dacin, M., & Mataer, M. (2010). Social entrepreneurship: Why don't we need a new theory and how we move forward from here. *Academy of Management Perspectives*, 24(3), 37-57.
- Department of Agriculture and Agrifood. (2018). Retrieved from <http://www.agriculture.gov.bn/SiteCollectionDocuments/Statistik/Agriculture%20and%20Agrifood%20Statistics%20in%20Brief%202018.pdf>
- Department of Economic Planning and Development. (2020). Retrieved from <http://www.deps.gov.bn/SitePages/eData%20library.aspx#collapseEconomy>
- Fairbank, J. F., & Williams, S. D. (2001). Motivating creativity and enhancing innovation through employee suggestion system technology. *Creativity and Innovation Management*, 10(2), 68–74. doi:10.1111/1467-8691.00204
- Guest, D. (2002). Human resource management, corporate performance and employee wellbeing: Building the worker into HRM. *Journal of Industrial Relations*, 44(3), 335–358. doi:10.1111/1472-9296.00053
- Herbel, D., Croweley, E., & Lee, M. (2010). *Good practices in building innovative rural institutions to increase food security*. FAO Issue.
- Musa, S. F. P. D., Idris, P. S. R. P. H., & Basir, K. H. (2020). Exploring the Entrepreneurial Motivations and Barriers of Agripreneurs in Brunei Darussalam. In *Economics, Business, and Islamic Finance in ASEAN Economics Community* (pp. 31-56). IGI Global.
- Musa, S. F. P. D. H., Pg Hj Idris, P. S. R., & Basir, K. H. (2020). *Inspiring Agripreneurs of Brunei*. UNISSA Press, Universiti Islam Sultan Sharif Ali.
- Stimpson, P., & Farquharson, A. (2010). *Business Studies: Cambridge International AS and A Level*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press, 2010.